

Studies in the Synthesis of Furochromones. Part III. Kostanecki-Robinson Acetylation of *o*-Hydroxy Acylbenzofurans

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6-Hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran, 6-hydroxy-5-propionyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran, 4-hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,6-dimethylbenzofuran, 6-hydroxy-7-propionyl-benzofuran and 6-hydroxy-7-propionyl-3-methylbenzofuran, on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation and benzoylation gave the corresponding furochromones and furoflavones, the structures of which were confirmed by I.R. spectra.

In recent years furobenzo- γ -pyrones or furochromones have received considerable attention as they not only occur in nature but also possess therapeutic properties¹⁻³. In continuation of our work on the synthesis of furochromones⁴ we report here the synthesis of linear as well as angular furochromones by the application of Kostanecki-Robinson reaction on *o*-hydroxyacylbenzofurans, which were obtained by the alkaline hydrolysis of the corresponding *o*-hydroxyacyl-3-bromocoumarin derivatives⁵. It has been found that in all the cases furobenzo- γ -pyrone is the only product formed and in no case, furobenzo- α -pyrone or a mixture of furobenzo- γ -pyrone and furobenzo- α -pyrone is formed as reported by Limaye and Sathe⁶. This is supported by the I.R. Spectra of the products, which show strong band in the carbonyl region around 1650 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $> \text{C} = \text{O}$ group).

6-Hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran⁵ (Ia) when subjected to Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation with acetic anhydride and sodium acetate gave a product, which was insoluble in cold dilute alkali and did not develop any colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride solution. The product is assigned 6-acetyl-3,7,9-trimethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)-benzopyran structure (IIa). The i.r. spectrum of (IIa) showed two strong bands in the carbonyl region, viz., 1690 cm^{-1} (acetyl group at position 6) and 1645 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $> \text{C} = \text{O}$ groups). Attempts to deacetylate this either by sodium carbonate or con. sulphuric acid were unsuccessful.

6-Hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran (Ia) on Kostanecki-Robinson benzoylation with benzoic anhydride and sodium benzoate, gave 7-phenyl-3,9-dimethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g) benzopyran (IIb). The i.r. spectrum showed a strong band in the carbonyl region viz. 1645 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $> \text{C} = \text{O}$ group). 6-Benzoyl derivative could not be isolated in this case. Similarly 6-hydroxy-5-propionyl-3,7-dimethylbenzofuran⁵ (Ib) on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation and benzoylation afforded 3,6,7,9-tetramethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g) benzopyran (IIc) and 7-phenyl-3,6,9-trimethyl-5-oxo-5H-furo(3,2-g)benzopyran (IIId) respectively.

6-Hydroxy-7-propionylbenzofuran⁵ (Ic) when subjected to Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation and benzoylation yielded 7,8-dimethyl-9-oxo-9H-furo(2,3-f) benzopyran (IIIa) and

7-phenyl-8-methyl-9-oxo-9H-furo(2,3-f) benzopyran (IIIb) respectively. 3,7,9-Trimethyl-9-oxo-9H-furo (2,3-f) benzopyran (IIIe) was similarly prepared from 6-hydroxy-7-propionyl-3-methylbenzofuran (Id).

4-Hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,6-dimethylbenzofuran (Ie) on Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation gave 6-acetyl-3,5,8-trimethyl-7oxo-7H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran (IVa) which showed two strong bands in the carbonyl region viz. 1690 cm^{-1} (acetyl group at position 6) and 1640 cm^{-1} (γ -pyronyl $>C=O$ group). Attempts to deacetylate this either by sodium carbonate or con. sulphuric acid were unsuccessful. 4-Hydroxy-5-acetyl-3,6-dimethylbenzofuran (Ie) when subjected to Kostanecki -Robinson benzoylation gave 5-phenyl-3,8-dimethyl-7-oxo-7H-furo (2,3-h) benzopyran (IVb).

- I a : $R = R_4 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_1 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{OH}$; $R_2 = \text{COCH}_3$
 b : $R = R_4 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_4 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{OH}$; $R_2 = \text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_3$
 c : $R = R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{OH}$; $R_4 = \text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_3$
 d : $R = \text{CH}_3$; $R_1 = R_2 = \text{H}$; $R_3 = \text{OH}$; $R_4 = \text{COCH}_2\text{CH}_3$
 e : $R = R_3 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_4 = \text{H}$; $R_1 = \text{OH}$; $R_2 = \text{COCH}_3$

- II a : $R = \text{CH}_3$; $R_1 = \text{COCH}_3$
 b : $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $R_1 = \text{H}$
 c : $R = R_1 = \text{CH}_3$
 d : $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $R_1 = \text{H}$

- III a : $R = R_1 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_2 = \text{H}$
 b : $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $R_1 = \text{CH}_3$; $R_2 = \text{H}$
 c : $R = R_1 = R_2 = \text{CH}_3$

- IV a : $R = \text{CH}_3$; $R_1 = \text{COCH}_3$
 b : $R = \text{C}_6\text{H}_5$; $R_1 = \text{H}$

E X P E R I M E N T A L

The i.r. spectra were recorded on Perkin Elmer 237 grating spectrophotometer in nujol.

The compounds were also tested for their purity on T L C , which showed only one spot.

Kostanecki-Robinson acetylation : A mixture of *o*-hydroxy-acylbenzofuran (1 g.), freshly fused sodium acetate (3 g.) and acetic anhydride (8 ml.) was heated at 180°–90° in an oil bath for 10 to 12 hrs. After cooling, the reaction mixture was poured into crushed ice. The separated product was filtered, washed with dilute alkali solution to remove unreacted compound and then with water. The dried product was dissolved in benzene and the solution was run over a short column of alumina. After evaporation of the solvent, the residue crystallised from acetic acid. M.P. yields are recorded in Table 1.

TABLE 1

Kostanecki-Robinson acylation of o-hydroxyacylbenzofurans

Compound	M.P. °C	Yield g	Molecular formula	Analysis			
				Found		Required	
				Carbon %	Hydrogen %	Carbon %	Hydrogen %
IIa	175	0.5	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄	71.41	4.96	71.10	5.10
IIb	268	0.5	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₃	78.66	5.06	78.61	4.82
IIc	215	0.6	C ₁₃ H ₁₄ O ₃	74.30	5.70	74.39	5.78
IId	244	0.5	C ₂₀ H ₁₆ O ₃	78.71	5.06	78.93	5.26
IIIa	227	0.4	C ₁₃ H ₁₀ O ₃	72.97	4.97	72.90	4.67
IIIb	144	0.4	C ₁₈ H ₁₂ O ₃	77.88	4.18	78.27	4.34
IIIc	196	0.5	C ₁₄ H ₁₂ O ₃	73.96	5.24	73.69	5.26
IVa	165	0.6	C ₁₆ H ₁₄ O ₄	70.99	5.27	71.10	5.10
IVb	above 350 (decomp.)	0.4	C ₁₉ H ₁₄ O ₃	78.81	4.60	78.61	4.82

Kostanecki-Robinson benzylation : A mixture of *o*-hydroxy acylbenzofuran (1 g.), freshly fused sodium benzoate (3 g.) and benzoic anhydride (3 g.) was heated in an oil bath for 10–12 hrs. The reaction mixture was worked up as usual. A benzene solution of the product was passed over a short column of alumina. The solid which separated on evaporation of the solvent, crystallised from acetic acid. M.P. yields etc. are recorded in Table 1.

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